

Defensive Analysis: Soundness in Extreme Conditions

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Abstract

Virtually no realistic whole-program static analysis is sound, i.e., guaranteed to over-approximate all program behaviors. The main cause of such unsoundness is “opaque code” features such as reflection, dynamic loading, and native calls.

We present a defensive may-point-to analysis approach, which offers soundness in the presence of opaque code. Our analysis assumes (unless informed otherwise) that native code or reflection can have arbitrary effects, and arbitrary new code can be loaded.

The analysis represents points-to information only when it knows it to be a safe over-approximation of dynamic behavior. This allows us to perform a highly precise points-to analysis (such as a 5-call-site-sensitive, flow-sensitive analysis) efficiently. We show that sound handling of opaque code cannot be an incremental addition: the analysis logic for other language features changes radically when opaque code needs to be handled soundly.

Despite its conservative nature, our analysis yields sound, actionable results for a large subset of the program code, achieving (under worst-case assumptions) 34-74% of the program coverage of an unsound state-of-the-art analysis for real-world programs.

1. Introduction

Static program analysis is an established research area, with a history tracing back to several decades and applications in virtually all modern programming technologies. Static analysis attempts to answer questions about program behavior under all possible inputs. Therefore, virtually all interesting static program analysis questions are undecidable—indeed the prototypical undecidable problem, the *halting problem*, is a static program analysis question: will a program terminate under all inputs?

Since static analysis attempts to solve undecidable problems, practical analysis algorithms are of one of two categories: either the analysis *under-approximates* the precise answer, in which case it is called a *must-analysis*, or it *over-approximates* the precise answer, in which case it is called a *may-analysis*.

It is therefore rather surprising that practically *no* implemented whole-program static may-analysis is *sound*, i.e., correctly does what it claims, for realistic programs [16]. For instance, a may-analysis should be over-approximate, but no realistic may-point-to analysis truly computes an over-approximation of the actual points-to sets that arise during program execution.

The main culprit for this apparent paradox is complex language features, such as native (non-analyzable) code, dynamic loading, reflection, as well as instructions such as `invokedynamic`. In the context of this paper, we will collectively refer to these features as *opaque code*.

It is tempting to attempt to dismiss opaque code as an engineering complication: analyses as published do not support these features, but surely it must be a straightforward addition to support them in the implementation? This is far from the case, however. Opaque code cannot be handled soundly without a fundamentally different approach to static analysis. Furthermore, the traditional handling of opaque code is not merely unsound, but also imprecise, making the analysis much less scalable.

To see this, consider the conventional handling of reflection in may-point-to analysis algorithms for Java [6, 12–15, 24]. The approach of past analyses has been to attempt to statically model the result of reflection operations, e.g., by computing a superset of the strings that can be used as arguments to a `Class.forName` operation (which accepts a name string and returns a reflection object representing the class with that name).

This past approach is a) ineffective; b) inefficient; and c) fundamentally hopeless for soundness. First, past analyses are not truly over-approximate. For instance, even though the analysis computes a superset of *constant* strings that are used as reflection arguments, when faced with a completely unknown string, the analysis does not assume that *any* class object can be returned, but rather that *none* can. The reason is that over-approximation (assuming any object is returned) would be detrimental to the analysis performance and precision. Second, even with an unsound approach, current algorithms are heavily burdened by the use of reflection analysis. For instance, the documentation of the WALA library directly blames reflection analysis for scalability short-

comings,¹ and enabling reflection on the DOOP framework slows it down by an order of magnitude on standard benchmarks [24]. Most importantly, however, no such approach can possibly ever be sound purely statically. Even if the analysis could feasibly assume that *any* class object is returned by a `forName` operation, this cannot account for dynamically generated and loaded classes—a ubiquitous feature in Java enterprise applications.

In response to the above need, we propose *defensive analysis*: a static analysis architecture that aims for sound handling of opaque code. To achieve this goal, defensive analysis has a strikingly different logical form. Instead of adding sophisticated handling of opaque code, defensive analysis redefines the analysis logic *for all other language features*, to defensively protect against the possibility that the analysis information potentially depends on opaque code.

We designed and implemented a defensive may-point-to (henceforth just “points-to”) analysis for Java. The analysis guarantees that any points-to set it computes is over-approximate, i.e., captures all possible dynamic behaviors.

In order to address the dual issues of efficiency and lack of information about dynamic loading, the analysis represents points-to sets with an unbounded number of objects (e.g., sets that depend on reflection or dynamic loading) as the empty set. That is, when the analysis infers that a variable can point to *anything*, it assigns it an *empty* points-to set. This choice may at first seem rather counter-intuitive, but it yields several significant advantages. First, the approach acquires an intuitive interpretation if one views empty points-to sets as signifying “don’t know”/“cannot bound” values: an empty set simply implies that the analysis has failed to upper-bound its contents. Second, this representation yields very compact points-to sets, since unbounded ones are over-approximated *implicitly* (i.e., without an explicit enumeration of their contents). Third, the approach allows the core of the analysis logic to be monotonic (“if the set includes some value then ...”), allowing for its efficient implementation with generic fixpoint machinery, such as a Datalog engine.

In terms of applications, soundness is an absolute requirement for ambitious analysis clients, such as automatic optimization or semantics-preserving refactoring. Such clients are simply not feasible with prior analysis approaches. In particular, inter-procedural automatic optimization has long been hindered by the absence of sound points-to analysis information. Thus, our work has significant potential for wide practical application.

Concretely, our work makes the following contributions:

- We offer the first realistic, general static may-point-to analysis that is sound in the presence of opaque code.² Our

¹“Reflection usage and the size of modern libraries/frameworks make it very difficult to scale flow-insensitive points-to analysis to modern Java programs.” [6]

²Arguably other approaches achieve soundness, but not for the full problem. For instance, Hirzel et al. [8, 9] use an online pointer analysis to deal

approach is based on a different architecture that is likely to be a blueprint for a variety of other sound analyses.

- We show that the analysis, though quite defensive, yields useful coverage. In measurements over large Java benchmarks, our analysis computes guaranteed over-approximate points-to sets for 34-74% of the local variables of a conventional unsound analysis. (This number is much higher than that of a conventional sound but *intra-procedural* analysis.) Similar effectiveness is achieved for other metrics (e.g., number of calls de-virtualized), again with actionable, guaranteed-sound outcomes. Finally, our analysis is efficient, due to its tight representation of points-to sets: we evaluate a highly precise flow-sensitive, 5-call-site-sensitive defensive analysis, which would be too heavyweight for typical past approaches.
- The work brings clarity to the domain of static analysis of opaque code. Our approach allows, for the first time, to quantitatively weigh the benefits of sound inter-procedural analysis against its costs and decide whether unsoundness is tolerable, or a fully sound approach is preferable.

2. Illustration of the Approach

Before we present our analysis in full detail, it is instructive to illustrate its behavior with representative examples.

Our analysis is a may-point-to analysis based on access paths, i.e., expressions of the form “`var(.fld)*`”. As is common, the analysis computes the abstract objects (corresponding to allocation sites in the program text) that an access path may point to. The analysis is *flow-sensitive*, hence we will be computing points-to information separately for each point in the program.

Examples. Consider first the case of merging information from two different control-flow paths. When both points-to sets involved have known upper bounds, the defensive analysis behaves just like a traditional analysis, taking the union of the two sets:

```
1 if (complexCondition()) {
2   x = new A(); // abstract object a1
3   // x points-to set is {a1}
4 } else {
5   x = new B(); // abstract object b1
6   // x points-to set is {b1}
7 }
8 // x points-to set is {a1,b1}
```

The difference arises when one of the two control-flow paths employs opaque code. We use an imaginary call

with reflection and dynamic loading by monitoring their run-time occurrence, recording their results, and running the analysis again, incrementally. However, this is hardly a *static* analysis and its cost is prohibitive for precise (context-sensitive) analyses, if applied to all reflection actions. Lattner et al. [11] offer an algorithm that can apply to incomplete programs, but it assumes that the linker can know all callers (i.e., there is no reflection—the analysis is for C/C++) and the approach is closely tied to a specific flow-insensitive, unification-based analysis logic, necessary for simultaneously computing inter-related points-to, may-alias, and may-escape information.

`opaque()` to signify the cause of loss of analysis information, such as a use of reflection, a native call, and more.

```
1 if (complexCondition()) {
2   x = new A(); // abstract object a1
3   // x points-to set is {a1}
4 } else {
5   x = opaque();
6   // x points-to set is {}
7 }
8 // x points-to set is {}
```

The first branch of the above `if` expression establishes that the points-to set of variable `x` is `{a1}`, i.e., the singleton containing the allocation site for `A` objects on line 2. The second branch, however, has an unbounded points-to set for `x`, since the branch involves `opaque` code. Our analysis uses the empty set to denote a “don’t know”/“cannot bound” inference result. At the control-flow merge point, a traditional points-to analysis would infer that `x` points to `a1` as well as to whatever other abstract objects are computed as the best-effort approximation of the effects of the `opaque` code. In contrast, our defensive analysis computes an *empty* points-to set for `x` at the merge point: the points-to set cannot be bounded. Hence, under defensive analysis, merging a points-to set of `{a1}` and an empty points-to set does not yield their union (as in a conventional unsound analysis), but instead the empty set.

Importantly, computing an empty points-to set requires no inference: it is just the result of not succeeding in inferring a points-to relationship of `x` with *any* abstract object. This means that the analysis logic is monotonic, as we will see in the next section. The logic is merely of the form “if two branches are merged, one has `x` point to object `o` and the other has `x` point to *something*, then `x` also points to `o` at the merge point”.

Similar treatment applies to all cases of points-to sets (e.g., for complex access paths) when information is merged: the analysis yields a result *only if it is certain* that the result is an over-approximation of the dynamic behavior. Otherwise, it produces nothing, i.e., an empty points-to set. Indeed, a constant theme throughout the analysis logic will be to eagerly fall back to computing nothing when the analysis is uncertain. Uncertainty regarding the upper bound of a points-to set can be due to many factors, not just control-flow merging. For instance, consider the following example of heap store instructions:

```
1 x.fld = new A(); // abstract object a1
2 // x.fld points-to set is {a1}
3 y.fld = opaque();
4 // x.fld points-to set is {}
```

After the first instruction, the points-to set of access path `x.fld` is computed to be `{a1}`. However, in most cases, the analysis will not be able to ascertain that `x` and `y` are not aliased. Therefore, after the second instruction, the points-to set of `x.fld` will be empty, i.e., unknown.

Generally, since the analysis is access-path based, store instructions certain to operate on the same object perform *strong updates*, while store instructions that *possibly* operate on the same object perform *weak updates*:

```
1 x.fld = new A(); // abstract object a1
2 // x.fld points-to set is {a1}
3 x.fld = new B(); // abstract object b1
4 // x.fld points-to set is {b1}
5 y.fld = new B(); // abstract object b2
6 // x.fld points-to set is {b1,b2}
```

In this case, the points-to information of access path `x.fld` is set to `{b1}` after the second store instruction, ignoring the previous contents. (The example assumes that types `A` and `B` are both compatible with the static type of `x.fld`.) After the third store instruction, however, a new element is added to the points-to set—again, under the assumption that the analysis cannot determine whether `x` and `y` are aliased.

As before, if any of the involved points-to sets is empty, both strong and weak updates yield an empty points-to set. For instance, replacing any of the three allocations above with a call to `opaque()` would make all subsequent points-to sets of `x.fld` be empty.

It is interesting to also consider how a defensive analysis needs to handle virtual calls. In a conventional unsound analysis, virtual calls can be analyzed based on available information. For instance, in the example below, any past analysis would resolve the virtual call `x.foo()` to, at least, the method `A::foo`, i.e., `foo` in class `A`.

```
1 if (complexCondition()) {
2   x = new A(); // abstract object a1
3 } else {
4   x = opaque();
5 }
6 x.foo();
```

In contrast, recall that for a defensive analysis the points-to set of `x` at the point of the call to `foo` is empty. Accordingly, the defensive analysis does *not* resolve the virtual call at all. This means that all heap information (i.e., all access-path points-to information, except for *trivial* access paths consisting of a single local variable and no fields) that held before the method call ceases to hold after it!³

This approach may seem extreme, but it is the only behavior consistent with a defensive analysis. The principle remains: if the analysis cannot over-approximate a points-to set, it falls back to computing nothing, i.e., an empty set.

It is natural to wonder if some other conservative approach is possible for virtual call resolution. Namely, for conservative call-graph construction, one can employ algorithms such as *Class Hierarchy Analysis (CHA)* [5] or *Rapid Type Analysis (RTA)* [1]. *CHA* explores the entire class hierarchy for matching (overriding) methods and considers all of

³There are notable exceptions—e.g., for access paths with final fields, or for cases when an escape analysis can establish that some part of the heap does not escape into the called method. Section 4 discusses such intricacies.

them to be potential virtual call targets. However, even this is not sufficient for a sound static analysis of opaque code: classes can be generated and loaded dynamically during program execution. CHA cannot find target methods that do not even exist statically, yet modeling them is precisely what is needed for soundness in real-world conditions! For instance, Java applications, especially in the enterprise (server-side) space, employ dynamic loading heavily, and patterns such as *dynamic proxies* have been standardized and used widely since the early Java days.

Furthermore, such heuristic “best-effort” over-approximation is detrimental to analysis precision and performance. CHA is an example of a loose over-approximation in an effort to capture most dynamic behaviors. Loose over-approximations compute many more possible targets than those that realistically arise. This yields vast points-to sets that render the analysis heavyweight and useless due to imprecision. (Avoiding such costs is exactly why past analyses have often opted for glaringly unsound handling of opaque code features.) Our representation of “don’t know”/“cannot bound” values as empty sets addresses the problem, by keeping all points-to sets compact.

Analogous issues arise when considering the propagation of analysis inferences to *resolved* method calls. A defensive analysis may know all methods that can get called at a certain point, but it cannot know all callers of a method. Consider the following example:

```

1  static void callee(A y) { ... }
2  static void caller() {
3    A x = new A(); // abstract object a1
4    callee(x); // static call to callee
5  }

```

Assume that there is no other call to `callee` anywhere in the program. An unsound analysis would establish that variable `y` in `callee` points to abstract object `a1`. A defensive analysis, however, cannot do the same unconditionally. The points-to set of `y` without context information has to be the empty set! The reason is that there may be unknown callers of `callee`: either in existing code, via reflection, or in dynamically loaded code. Such callers could pass different objects as arguments to `callee` and the analysis cannot upper-bound the set of such arguments. Thus, the only safe answer for a defensive analysis is “don’t know”/“cannot bound”—i.e., an empty set.

In order to propagate analysis results inter-procedurally, a defensive analysis makes extensive use of context information. In the above example, what the analysis will establish is that `y` points to `a1` *conditionally*, under context 4, signifying the call-site instruction (line 4 in our listing). (We denote this “ $4 \vdash y \rightarrow a1$ ”.)

The above implies that the use of context in a defensive analysis is rather different than in a traditional unsound points-to analysis. Contexts in standard points-to analysis (e.g., see [10] for a general model) can be *summarizing*: a

single context can merge arbitrary concrete (dynamic) executions, as long as any single concrete execution maps uniquely to a context. For instance, a 1-object-sensitive analysis [18] merges all calls to a method as long as they have the same abstract receiver object, independently of call sites.

Context in a conventional analysis only adds *precision*, relative to a context-insensitive analysis. In contrast, context in a defensive analysis is necessary for *correctness*: since information is collected per-program-point, propagating points-to sets from a call site to a callee can only be done under a context that identifies the call-site program point. Contexts cannot freely summarize multiple invocation instructions, because there may be others, yet unknown, invocations that would result in the same context.

Therefore, a context-sensitive defensive analysis has to be, at a minimum, *call-site sensitive* [21, 22]: the call site of an analyzed method has to be part of the context (as well as, for deeper context, the call site of the caller, the call site of the caller’s caller, etc.). Other kinds of context (e.g., object-sensitive context [18]) can be added for extra precision, but call-sites cannot be dropped.

Note how the above example (of potentially unknown callers) does not contain an `opaque()` call or other direct source of unknown values. This illustrates a more general insight: in a defensive analysis (unlike in, say, a *taint analysis*), “don’t know”/“cannot bound” values are not produced only by known sources, but also by *the absence of precise analysis information*, for any reason. Notably, the analysis may not have precise information because it has reached its maximum context depth. Consider the case of analyzing the following code fragment, with bounded context of maximum depth 1, under context `c`. We begin with the assumption that, under `c`, variable `y` points to abstract object `a1`.

```

1  // c |- y points-to set is {a1}
2  x.fld = y;
3  // c |- x.fld points-to set is {a1}
4  callee(); // max context depth = 1
5  // c |- x.fld points-to set is {}

```

During analysis, the call to `callee` cannot be analyzed because the maximum context depth of the analysis has been reached. In response, the points-to information of access path `x.fld` (and of any other complex access path) is set to “don’t know”/“cannot bound”. Again, the choice to represent such values with the empty set is highly convenient: inability to compute something (i.e., an upper bound for the points-to set contents) means computing nothing, i.e., a “don’t know”/“cannot bound” value.

The above examples are not exhaustive. Other cases of absence of precise information arise. For instance, the analysis does not have precise information at possible interference points from other threads, loads from access paths with no definite points-to information, etc. The analysis will naturally default to computing the empty set in each case.

Observations. There are some general observations to be made regarding the defensive analysis approach.

First, a defensive analysis is naturally modular. It can be applied to any subset of the code of an application or library and it will produce sound inferences. Omitting code merely means that more points-to sets will end up being empty. Therefore, a useful concept is that of the analysis’s *coverage*: for how many program elements (e.g., local variables) can the analysis produce non-empty points-to information?

Furthermore, a defensive analysis is not in competition with a conventional, unsound analysis, but instead complements it. The defensive analysis computes which of the points-to sets have known upper bounds and which are potentially undetermined. If, instead of an empty set, a client desires to receive the (incomplete) subset of known contents for “don’t know/cannot bound” points-to sets, the results of the two analyses can be trivially combined.

3. Analysis Model

We next present a rigorous model of our defensive analysis. The model is expressed in the Datalog language. Since the early work of Reps [20], Datalog has often been used to express program analysis algorithms (e.g., [4, 17, 26, 27]). The language captures well the usual program analysis notion of monotonic iteration until fixpoint. Datalog rules infer more facts from combinations of previously established facts, with variables implicitly quantified existentially. A rule of the form “ $\text{HEAD}(x,y) \leftarrow \text{P}(x,z), \text{Q}(y,z)$.” means that if values for x,y,z can be found so that $\text{P}(x,z)$ and $\text{Q}(y,z)$ are simultaneously true, then $\text{HEAD}(x,y)$ is inferred. Syntactically, the left arrow symbol (\leftarrow) separates the inferred facts (the *head* of the rule) from the previously established facts (the *body* of the rule). The program-under-analysis is represented as input relations (typically implemented as database tables) that encode its different elements. Such pre-processing is a relatively straightforward one-to-one translation.

3.1 Schema of Analysis Relations

Our model uses a minimal intermediate language that captures the essence of the approach. The language can be straightforwardly enhanced with features such as arrays, static members and calls, exceptions, etc. Indeed, our actual analysis implementation is on the Jimple intermediate language of the Soot framework [25], which models all features of Java bytecode. The specification of our analysis is in line with others in the literature [7, 10, 17]. We largely follow the schema and presentation pattern of Kastrinis et al. [10], so that we can draw attention to specific points of contrast between a conventional, unsound analysis and our defensive, sound one.

Figure 1 shows the domain of the analysis (i.e., the different value sets that constitute the space of our computation) and four different groups of relations.

V is a set of program variables	
M is a set of method identifiers	
S is a set of method signatures (including name, type signature)	
F is a set of fields	
I is a set of instructions	
T is a set of types	
C is a set of contexts	
A is a set of access paths (i.e., the set $V(.F)^*$)	
\mathbb{N} is the set of natural numbers	
<hr/>	
$\text{ALLOC}(i: I, \text{var}: V, \text{heap}: H)$	# $i: \text{var} = \text{new} \dots$
$\text{MOVE}(i: I, \text{to}: V, \text{from}: V)$	# $i: \text{to} = \text{from}$
$\text{LOAD}(i: I, \text{to}: V, \text{base}: V, \text{fld}: F)$	# $i: \text{to} = \text{base.fld}$
$\text{STORE}(i: I, \text{base}: V, \text{fld}: F, \text{from}: V)$	# $i: \text{base.fld} = \text{from}$
$\text{CALL}(i: I, \text{base}: V, \text{sig}: S)$	# $i: \text{base.sig}(\dots)$
$\text{UNKNOWN}(i: I)$	# $i: [\text{unknown instr.}]$
$\text{NEXT}(i: I, j: I)$	# j is CFG successor of i
<hr/>	
$\text{FORMALARG}(\text{meth}: M, n: \mathbb{N}, \text{arg}: V)$	
$\text{ACTUALARG}(\text{invo}: I, n: \mathbb{N}, \text{arg}: V)$	
$\text{FORMALRET}(\text{instr}: I, \text{meth}: M, \text{ret}: V)$	
$\text{ACTUALRET}(\text{invo}: I, \text{var}: V)$	
$\text{HEAPTYPE}(\text{heap}: H, \text{type}: T)$	
$\text{LOOKUP}(\text{type}: T, \text{sig}: S, \text{meth}: M)$	
$\text{INMETHOD}(\text{instr}: I, \text{meth}: M)$	
<hr/>	
$\text{POINTSTO}(\text{instr}: I, \text{ctx}: C, \text{ap}: A, \text{heap}: H)$	
$\text{BEFORE:POINTSTO}(\text{instr}: I, \text{ctx}: C, \text{ap}: A, \text{heap}: H)$	
$\text{CALLGRAPHEDGE}(\text{invo}: I, \text{ctx}: C, \text{toMeth}: M, \text{toCtx}: C)$	
$\text{REACHABLE}(\text{ctx}: C, \text{meth}: M)$	
$\text{REBASEAPFORRETURN}(\text{invo}: I, \text{fromAp}: A, \text{toAp}: A)$	
<hr/>	
$\text{AP}(\text{access path expression}) = \text{ap}: A$	
$\text{REBASEAP}(\text{ap}: A, \text{fromVar}: V, \text{toVar}: V) = \text{newAp}: A$	
$\text{NEWCONTEXT}(\text{invo}: I, \text{ctx}: C, \text{heap}: H) = \text{newCtx}: C$	
<hr/>	
$\text{ROOTMETHOD}(\text{meth}: M)$	

Figure 1: Our domain, input relations (ALLOC, ...), computed relations (POINTSTO, ...), constructors (AP, ...), and configuration predicate (ROOTMETHOD).

Input Relations. The input relations correspond to our intermediate language features. They are logically grouped into relations that represent instructions and relations that represent name-and-type information. For instance, the ALLOC relation represents every instruction, i , that allocates a new heap object, heap , and assigns it to local variable var . There are similar input relations for all other instruction types (MOVE, LOAD, STORE, and CALL). The UNKNOWN relation captures all instructions not known to the analysis. This gives us a general-purpose model of opaque code that is called explicitly. The NEXT relation expresses directed edges in the control-flow graph (CFG): $\text{NEXT}(i,j)$ means that i is a CFG predecessor of j .

Similarly, there are relations that encode type system, symbol table, and program environment information. FORMALARG shows which variable is a formal argument of a given method at a certain index (i.e., the n -th argument).

The relation is a function from the first two arguments to the third. `ACTUALARG` is similar, but at a method invocation site. The `this/base` variable of a method invocation is assumed to be the 0-th argument. `FORMALRET` combines information on the return variable of a method with the index of the return instruction. The input intermediate language program is assumed to be in a single-return-per-method form. `ACTUALRET` maps a method invocation site to the local variable that receives the method call’s return value. `HEAPTYPE` maps an abstract object to its type. `LOOKUP` is a function from its first two arguments to the third. It matches a method signature to the actual method definition inside a type. `INMETHOD` is a function from instructions to their containing methods.

Computed Relations. The main relation computed by the analysis is `POINTSTO`. It is our sound, flow-sensitive, context-sensitive may-point-to relation on access paths. The meaning of `POINTSTO(i, ctx, ap, heap)` is that access path *ap* points to abstract object *heap* right after program instruction *i*, executed under context *ctx*, provided that the instruction is indeed executed under *ctx* at program run-time. We also compute the same information *before* instruction *i* and capture it in relation `BEFORE:POINTSTO`. The interplay between `BEFORE:POINTSTO` and `POINTSTO` will define the analysis semantics of each language instruction.

Other computed relations represent intermediate results of the analysis. `CALLGRAPHEDGE` holds information for fully-resolved virtual calls: invocation site *invo* will call method *toMeth* under the given contexts. `REACHABLE` computes which methods and under what context are of interest to the analysis. `REBASEAPFORRETURN` is a helper relation that maps access paths of a callee back to those of a caller.

Constructors. We assume a constructor function `AP` that produces access paths, and another function `REBASEAP` that takes an access path and returns a new one by changing the base variable of the original. For instance, inside a logic program, “`AP(var,fld1,fld2) = ap`” means that the access path *ap* has length 3 and its elements are given by the values of bound logical variables *var*, *fld1* and *fld2*. Similarly, we construct new contexts using function `NEWCONTEXT`. The above constructor functions also serve to configure the analysis. If a constructor does not return a value (e.g., because the maximum context depth has been reached), the current rule employing the constructor will not produce facts. The constant `ALL` is used to signify the initial context.

We shall also use `AP` as a pattern matcher over access paths. For instance, the expression “`AP(_,fld) = ap`” binds the value of logical variable *fld* to any field of access path *ap*. (*_* is an anonymous variable that can match any value in a Datalog program.)

In practical analyses, the space of access paths is made finite, by bounding their length, and similarly for contexts.

Configuration. The last part of Figure 1 shows an initialization predicate, `ROOTMETHOD`. Our defensive analysis can be applied to any subset of the code. The initial set of methods to examine are given in `ROOTMETHOD`. Our algorithm will venture beyond these root methods only to the extent that its analysis context depth allows.

3.2 Analysis Model

Figures 2 and 3 show our analysis algorithm. To keep the rules concise, we have employed some syntactic sugar:

- In addition to conjunction (signified by the usual “;” in a rule body) our rules also employ disjunction (“;”) and negation (“!”). Negation is stratified: it is only applied to predicates that are either input predicates or whose computation can complete before the current rule’s evaluation. We also allow multiple predicates in the head of a rule. This is equivalent to splitting the rule into multiple ones with the same body, for each one of the heads.
- We freely use quantifiers \forall and \exists in rules. The use of \exists is a shorthand that avoids introducing an intermediate helper rule for the corresponding concept. The use of \forall is syntactic sugar⁴ that hides a Datalog pattern for enumerating all members of a set and checking a condition over them. An expression “ $\forall i: P(i) \rightarrow Q(i, \dots)$ ” is true if $Q(i, \dots)$ holds for all *i* for which $P(i)$ holds. Such an expression can be used in a rule body, as a condition for the rule’s firing. Multiple variables can be quantified by a \forall . If a variable is not bound in the body of a \forall , it remains implicitly existentially quantified, as in conventional Datalog. However, the existential quantifier is interpreted as being outside the universal one. For instance, “ $\forall i, j: P(i, j, k) \rightarrow Q(i, j, k, l)$ ” is interpreted as “there exist *k, l* such that for all *i, j* ...”.

Before we delve into the rules themselves, some high-level comments will help their understanding. The rules are presented in roughly increasing order of complexity.

As we will see, the rules contain little explicit handling of `UNKNOWN` instructions. Instead, the defensive approach is weaved throughout the analysis, affecting several different rules: for control-flow merging, for returns from calls, for heap store instructions, etc. The invariant maintained throughout is that the `POINTSTO` relation always holds an over-approximation of the possible abstract objects in an access path’s points-to set, or nothing, if an over-approximation is not possible.

Base rules and heap handling. The first group of rules (top of Figure 2) is straightforward and hardly different from a conventional points-to analysis. The analysis is kick-started by considering all “root” methods (specified by the `ROOTMETHOD` configuration predicate) to be reachable, under the empty context (`ALL`). Points-to information is computed only for reachable methods. The next two rules in the

⁴There is one exception of a non-monotonic use of \forall , which is discussed separately in Section 4.

REACHABLE(**ALL**, *meth*) \leftarrow ROOTMETHOD(*meth*).

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, **AP**(*var*), *heap*) \leftarrow
 ALLOC(*i*, *var*, *heap*), INMETHOD(*i*, *meth*),
 REACHABLE(*ctx*, *meth*).

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *toAp*, *heap*) \leftarrow
 MOVE(*i*, *to*, *from*),
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *fromAp*, *heap*),
 REBASEAP(*fromAp*, *from*, *to*) = *toAp*.

NEWCONTEXT(*i*, *ctx*, *heap*) = *toCtx*,
 CALLGRAPHEDGE(*i*, *ctx*, *toMeth*, *toCtx*),
 REACHABLE(*toCtx*, *toMeth*) \leftarrow
 CALL(*i*, *base*, *sig*),
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, **AP**(*base*), *heap*),
 HEAPTYPE(*heap*, *type*), LOOKUP(*type*, *sig*, *toMeth*).

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, **AP**(*to*), *heap*) \leftarrow
 LOAD(*i*, *to*, *base*, *fld*),
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, **AP**(*base.fld*), *heap*).

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, **AP**(*base.fld*), *heap*) \leftarrow
 STORE(*i*, *base*, *fld*, *from*),
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, **AP**(*from*), *heap*).

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap1*),
 POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap2*) \leftarrow
 STORE(*i*, *base*, *fld*, *from*),
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, **AP**(*from*), *heap1*),
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap2*),
 $ap = \mathbf{AP}(base'.fld)$, $base \neq base'$.

BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*) \leftarrow
 NEXT(*pred*, *i*),
 POINTSTO(*pred*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*),
 $(\forall j: \text{NEXT}(j, i) \rightarrow \text{POINTSTO}(j, \text{ctx}, \text{ap}, _))$.

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*) \leftarrow
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*), $ap = \mathbf{AP}(var)$,
 !LOAD(*i*, *var*, $_$, $_$), !MOVE(*i*, *var*, $_$),
 !ALLOC(*i*, *var*, $_$), !UNKNOWN(*i*).

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*) \leftarrow
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*), $ap = \mathbf{AP}(var._)$,
 !CALL(*i*, $_$, $_$), !STORE(*i*, $_$, $_$, $_$), !LOAD(*i*, *var*, $_$, $_$),
 !MOVE(*i*, *var*, $_$), !ALLOC(*i*, *var*, $_$), !UNKNOWN(*i*).

POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*) \leftarrow
 STORE(*i*, $_$, *fld*, $_$),
 BEFORE:POINTSTO(*i*, *ctx*, *ap*, *heap*),
 $ap = \mathbf{AP}(_)$, $ap \neq \mathbf{AP}(_fld)$.

Figure 2: Model defensive analysis: handling alloc, move, load, store instructions and propagation to next instruction.

first group handle allocation and move instructions straightforwardly. The last rule establishes call-graph edges when a call instruction on a variable with a known points-to set is found. These call-graph edges will be used to propagate points-to information inter-procedurally, using the rules of Figure 3. The context constructor, **NEWCONTEXT**, is used in the head of the rule and its exact definition will determine the context-sensitivity of the analysis.

The second group of rules in Figure 2 (middle) begins to exhibit features of our defensive analysis. The rules handle heap load and store instructions. A load instruction is straightforward: if there is points-to information for an access path, it is inferred for the trivial access path consisting of the *to* variable.

Store instructions illustrate the strong and weak updates shown in our examples of Section 2. The first “store” rule infers that the access path stored-to will point to the elements of the set in the access path of the *from* variable. Combined with the absence of logic to propagate the old value of the stored-to access path, this rule is responsible for strong updates of the points-to information. (As we discuss in Section 4, this rule can be generalized to also take into account the results of a must-alias analysis.)

The second “store” rule performs weak updates for access paths that may alias (although their bases are different). When there is before-points-to information for an access path over the same field, the information is propagated after the store instruction, *and* augmented with the points-to set of the *from* variable of the store. Note how the rule is simultaneously defensive and monotonic (with no use of negation): if the *from* variable does not have an upper-bounded points-to set, the original access path’s (*ap*) points-to information is *not* propagated beyond the store instruction—that points-to set is now also possibly unbounded, i.e., empty.

Frame rules: propagating to the next instruction. The third group of rules in Figure 2 (bottom part) are *frame rules*, responsible for the propagation of unchanged information.

The first of these rules is highly representative of our defensive analysis. It infers BEFORE:POINTSTO information from POINTSTO at predecessors. The rule states that if some predecessor instruction, *pred*, has established that *ap* can point to *heap*, *and* if all other predecessors, *j*, establish that *ap* points to *something* (so that its points-to set is guaranteed to be bounded) then the information is propagated to the BEFORE:POINTSTO relation of the successor instruction.

The next three rules state that points-to information for trivial (single variable only) access paths is propagated over all instructions, unless these assign the variable or are unknown. (By convention, an “ $_$ ” under negation means “does not exist one” and not “exists one that does not...”.) Similarly, points-to information for complex access paths is propagated unless an instruction assigns the base variable, or is a call, store, or unknown. Finally, points-to information for

$$\begin{aligned}
&\text{POINTSTO}(fstInstr, toCtx, ap, heap) \leftarrow \\
&\text{CALLGRAPHEDGE}(i, ctx, toMeth, toCtx), \\
&\text{INMETHOD}(fstInstr, toMeth), (\forall k: \rightarrow !\text{NEXT}(k, fstInstr)), \\
&\text{BEFORE:POINTSTO}(i, ctx, callerAp, heap), \\
&\text{FORMALARG}(toMeth, n, toVar), \text{ACTUALARG}(i, n, var), \\
&\text{REBASEAP}(callerAp, var, toVar) = ap. \\
\\
&\text{REBASEAPFORRETURN}(i, ap, newAp) \leftarrow \\
&\text{CALLGRAPHEDGE}(i, _, toMeth, _), \\
&((\text{FORMALARG}(toMeth, n, var), \text{ACTUALARG}(i, n, toVar), \\
&\quad ap = \mathbf{AP}(_ _)); \\
&\quad (\text{ACTUALRET}(i, toVar), \text{FORMALRET}(ret, toMeth, var))), \\
&\text{REBASEAP}(ap, var, toVar) = newAp. \\
\\
&\text{POINTSTO}(i, ctx, ap, heap) \leftarrow \\
&\text{CALLGRAPHEDGE}(i, ctx, toMeth, toCtx), \\
&\text{FORMALRET}(ret, toMeth, _), \\
&\text{BEFORE:POINTSTO}(ret, toCtx, calleeAp, heap), \\
&\text{REBASEAPFORRETURN}(i, calleeAp, ap), \\
&(\forall toMeth', toCtx': \\
&\quad \text{CALLGRAPHEDGE}(i, ctx, toMeth', toCtx') \rightarrow \\
&\quad (\exists ret', calleeAp': \\
&\quad \quad \text{FORMALRET}(ret', toMeth', _), \\
&\quad \quad \text{BEFORE:POINTSTO}(ret', toCtx', calleeAp', _), \\
&\quad \quad \text{REBASEAPFORRETURN}(i, calleeAp', ap))).
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 3: Model analysis: handling calls and returns.

complex access paths is propagated over all store instructions that affect fields not participating in the access path.

Calls and returns. Figure 3 presents the rules handling points-to information propagation over calls and returns. All rules are predicated on having computed a `CALLGRAPHEDGE` (per Figure 2), i.e., having a guaranteed over-approximation of the targets of a virtual call.

The first rule propagates points-to information from caller to callee. The information is established for the first instruction of a called method. This is computed, by convention, as the only instruction in the method that has no CFG predecessors. All access paths in the caller are rebased, to map actual arguments to formals.

The last two rules work jointly. `REBASEAPFORRETURN` is a helper relation that performs the expected rebasings of access paths at a method return: complex access paths get rebased from formal to actual argument variables, while access paths involving the formal return variable (in the callee) are rebased to the actual (in the caller).

This relation is used in the final rule—the most intricate of our analysis. The rule is analogous to the earlier rule for control-flow merging, yet at the inter-procedural level. The rule states that if some callee has points-to information for access path ap at a return point, then this information is propagated to the caller, provided that *all other callees* also have *some* (i.e., non-empty) points-to information for

ap at their return point. (The access paths are rebased as appropriate for each callee.)

Note that the handling of a method return is the only point where a context can become stronger. Facts that were inferred to hold under the more specific $toCtx$ are now established, modulo rebasing, under ctx .

In summary, the analysis model has an elegant declarative formulation. It is (almost entirely) monotonic, only specifying what to infer when something is true, not when something is not true (except over previously computed relations).

4. Refinements, Extensions, and Discussion

The defensive analysis model of the previous section admits a large number of enhancements and refinements.

Static Single Assignment input. With minor adaptation, the analysis logic can work on static single assignment (SSA) input. Our implementation is indeed based on an SSA intermediate language. The benefit is that for trivial access paths (just a single variable) points-to information does not need to be kept per-instruction: the points-to set remains unchanged, since the variable is not re-assigned.

Monotonicity and pre-analysis. The last rule of Figure 3 is not monotonic. It uses \forall over the `CALLGRAPHEDGE` relation, even though the latter is being computed simultaneously with the `POINTSTO` relation. (\forall quantifiers are expressible in Datalog under the assumption that the relations in the expression body are computed in a previous stratum, during a static stratification of the program.) Intuitively, the problem is that we cannot know whether a `POINTSTO` inference using the last rule will not cause its own invalidation, because it introduces a new `CALLGRAPHEDGE` tuple that represents a call to a function with an unbounded (i.e., empty) points-to set for the access path in question.

There are several ways to address this non-monotonicity, with sound approximations. The approximation we currently use in our implementation is to employ a pre-analysis that computes a subset of the call-graph edges. (I.e., it computes the same sound superset of the callees as the full analysis, but for a subset of the call sites.) The pre-analysis models local assignments (allocations and move instructions) as well as specific inter-procedural assignments (e.g., of actual arguments to formals) but does not handle the heap. Based on this analysis, we determine call sites that are already fully resolved with less than our full logic. This subset of the full call-graph results is only used in the rule for back-propagating points-to information from callee to caller. In principle, this iteration could be repeated: a run of our may-point-to analysis can build a call-graph that is used to instantiate the next run of the analysis, etc.

Our pre-analysis also comes handy in expanding the reach of the analysis. One instance concerns the first rule of the bottom third of Figure 2. The rule shows how points-to information can propagate at control-flow merge points, if all

of the predecessors have some points-to information for the access path in question. This condition is too strict in practice: several predecessors will not have points-to information for an access path simply because the access path is not even defined for the predecessor branch (e.g., it is based on a local variable that is set on a different branch only). The pre-analysis allows us to conservatively detect when there is no path on which a predecessor may have affected the value of an access path. Using this information, we limit the \forall quantification of the rule to range over “relevant” predecessors.

Pragmatics. A full-fledged analysis should cover more language features than the model of Section 3. Our implementation handles, in a manner similar to the earlier rules, features such as static and special method invocations, static fields, constructors (initializing fields to `null`), and more. Of particular note are final instance and static fields, which allow propagating information in a lot more settings (e.g., even when the analysis context depth has been reached and points-to sets would normally default to empty after a call).

Why access-path-points-to? Our defensive analysis is access-path based, as opposed to instance-field based. That is, instead of inferences of the form “abstract object `a1` points to `a2` via field `f`” our analysis makes inferences of the form “program expression `v.f` points to `a2`”. We conjecture that this is a necessity for a sound analysis. The issue is one of logical quantification. What is the meaning of the sentence “abstract object `a1` points to `a2` via field `f`”? A natural definition is “some concrete object mapping to abstract object `a1` points via field `f` to some concrete object mapping to `a2`.” However, this definition is too weak to allow sound inferences at the point of a load instruction. An alternative definition is “all concrete objects mapping to abstract object `a1` point via field `f` to some concrete object mapping to `a2`.” However, this inference is impossible to establish soundly at any program point: even if all instances of the abstract object satisfy this property somewhere, there is virtually never a single point at which all instances simultaneously satisfy the inference. It is possible that, in future work, an analysis can distinguish the most recent instance of an object [2]. At present, however, the access path abstraction seems like a particularly good fit for our defensive analysis logic.

Multi-Threading. The topic of soundness under concurrent execution is rich and complicated, yet independent of the issues (opaque code) that our work addresses. So far we have assumed a simple concurrency model and have not delved into the complexity of the Java memory model. We currently drop all access-path-points-to inferences at the points of `monitorenter` and `monitorexit` instructions. In this way, our analysis is sound for programs that use standard Java mutexes to protect all shared memory accesses. Relaxing this assumption is a matter orthogonal to our work.

Contexts. Our context constructor, `NEWCONTEXT`, in Section 3, is modeled after the `MERGE` context constructor

in conventional unsound points-to analyses [10, 23]. However, as mentioned in Section 2, the resulting context has to uniquely determine the `invo` argument. That is, a defensive analysis has to be at least call-site sensitive, although other kinds of context sensitivity can be added for extra precision. Our implementation supports general context constructors but currently only employs call-site sensitivity.

We could similarly add a context-sensitive heap to our model, by qualifying all abstract objects with an `hctx` argument and employing a heap-context constructor on the rule for `ALLOC`. This addition is orthogonal to all other elements, therefore we chose not to burden the model with it. Our implementation has `hctx` arguments in all rules, but we have not yet experimented with a context-sensitive heap.

Access paths. The analysis formulation of Section 3 assumes that all access paths exist in advance. In our implementation, we instead create access paths lazily, as needed.

In fact, access paths with a length higher than 2 do not even arise in the analysis model as shown in Section 3. However, the model is suitable for integration with analyses that do employ longer access paths. A particularly good fit is a must-alias analysis on access paths. Such an analysis improves our may-point-to analysis in several ways: it helps analyze more load instructions; it helps perform strong updates at store instructions (when the base variable of the store is a must-alias with the base of an access path). We have integrated such a must-alias analysis in our implementation, but do not enable it by default due to currently high cost.

Manual modeling. The analysis model is by default defensive: when an unknown method call is encountered, the analysis assumes worst-case behavior with respect to its heap information. This can be relaxed arbitrarily by modeling system methods and annotating them appropriately. Possible information about calls includes “this library call does not affect user-level objects”, “this method only affects its arguments”, “this method does not affect static variables”, etc. Additional manual modeling includes library collections (including arrays) which can be represented as abstract objects.

Our current implementation does minimal modeling of library collections and annotates a handful of methods. A representative example is that of method `Float.floatToRawIntBits`. This native method is called by the implementation of the `put` operation in `Java HashMaps` and, since it is opaque, would prevent all propagation of points-to information beyond a `put` call.

In our current implementation, such annotation effort is very limited in scope and only serves as a proof-of-concept.

Escape analysis. The analysis model invalidates points-to information when faced with a method call it cannot analyze. This behavior can be relaxed by employing a sound may-escape analysis. If all prefixes of an access path refer to objects that cannot escape into an unknown method call, then the access path cannot be invalidated by the call. We do not

Benchmark	Variables analyzed						Avg. points-to over same vars				Time (s)			
	2objH (*ins.)	5def (†4def) some ctx	% of 2objH (*ins.)	5def (†4def) all ctx	% of 2objH (*ins.)	intra-proc must- point-to	% of 2objH (*ins.)	2objH (*ins.)	5def (†4def) some ctx	2objH (*ins.) all ctx	5def (†4def) all ctx	2objH (*ins.)	5def (†4def)	
DaCapo 2006-10-MR2	antlr	29060	15902	54.7%	14589	50.2%	8222	28.3%	1.55	1.13	1.10	1.01	382	329
	bloat	30216	12236	40.5%	9541	31.6%	5495	18.2%	5.29	1.83	2.12	1.02	4152	490
	chart	12199	5552	45.5%	4369	35.8%	2946	24.1%	1.37	1.29	1.09	1.09	685	430
	eclipse	18918	8598	45.4%	6707	35.5%	4610	24.4%	1.81	1.17	1.31	1.06	483	238
	fop	9832	7250	73.7%	4739	48.2%	3282	33.4%	1.43	1.39	1.03	1.00	1419	898
	hsqldb	2762	1610	58.3%	1428	51.7%	755	27.3%	1.10	1.04	1.04	1.01	236	257
	jython*	61997	21280	34.3%	16212	26.1%	12326	19.9%	30.98	2.02	6.05	1.01	655	460
	luindex	6880	3397	49.4%	2612	38.0%	1561	22.7%	1.22	1.13	1.02	1.02	197	197
	lusearch	9072	4014	44.2%	2994	33.0%	1849	20.4%	1.35	1.21	1.06	1.04	210	201
	pmd	15262	6143	40.3%	4617	30.3%	2920	19.1%	1.40	1.31	1.05	1.01	268	799
xalan	26470	9344	35.3%	6874	26.0%	5447	20.6%	2.55	1.76	1.12	1.05	440	578	
jFlex	7861	3594	45.7%	2866	36.5%	1992	25.3%	1.41	1.19	1.02	1.01	965	205	
NTI	3238	1934	59.7%	1404	43.4%	756	23.3%	1.47	1.42	1.03	1.03	189	97	
DaCapo 9.12-Bach	avrora	49917	24199	48.5%	17777	35.6%	11906	23.9%	3.31	1.55	3.04	1.05	2972	2162
	batik	55819	25312	45.3%	18754	33.6%	14252	25.5%	2.37	1.62	1.05	1.04	3078	1720
	eclipse	23218	10905	47.0%	8638	37.2%	6019	25.9%	1.96	1.19	1.53	1.07	787	592
	h2*	61465	24794	40.3%	19544	31.8%	11398	18.5%	5.29	1.35	2.07	1.04	533	1699
	luindex	13437	6242	46.5%	4890	36.4%	2970	22.1%	1.15	1.09	1.04	1.01	310	281
	lusearch	10656	5171	48.5%	3893	36.5%	2393	22.5%	1.28	1.15	1.08	1.03	338	258
	pmd	20042	7686	38.3%	5703	28.5%	3806	19.0%	1.39	1.23	1.04	1.01	624	893
	sunflow	12703	5901	46.5%	4312	33.9%	2872	22.6%	1.56	1.34	1.08	1.05	1313	499
	xalan†	86784	32841	37.8%	26285	30.3%	20630	23.8%	2.68	1.44	1.19	1.04	3051	4416
	median			45.6%		35.5%		23.0%						

Figure 4: Coverage of a defensive analysis (over variables reachable by unsound analysis), points-to set sizes for non-empty sets of common variables for both analyses, and running times of analyses. Min/max percentages shown in bold.

currently employ escape reasoning in our implementation, but this is a topic of active work.

5. Evaluation

We have built our defensive analysis framework over a flow-sensitive extension of the DOOP Datalog framework for may-point-to analysis of Java bytecode [4]. This gives us a standard platform for comparison with conventional (unsound) may-point-to analysis approaches. Our implementation is a non-trivial declarative specification. It consists of over 400 logical rules in 3KLoC, yet the minimal model of Section 3 captures well its essential features.

We use our algorithm to perform a highly precise, 5-call-site-sensitive, flow-sensitive defensive analysis (nicknamed *5def*), which we compare against two reference analyses:

- The standard DOOP framework 2-object-sensitive/heap-sensitive analysis (*2objH*). This is the most precise analysis in DOOP that still manages to scale to the majority of the DaCapo benchmarks. We use static best-effort reflection handling (`--enable-reflection-classic` flag), i.e., the analysis tries to statically resolve all reflection calls based on string matching.
- An intra-procedural must-point-to analysis. This analysis captures the low-hanging fruit of points-to reasoning: local variables that directly or transitively (via “move” instructions) get assigned an allocated object. Comparing

with this analysis shows how much our analysis benefits from its new elements: inter-procedural handling, as well as handling of control-flow merging. (Using this analysis as a baseline was suggested by a pointer analysis expert.)

We analyze, under JDK 1.7.0_75, the DaCapo benchmark programs [3] v.2006-10-MR2 as well as v.9.12-Bach. The 9.12-Bach version contains several different programs, as well as more recent versions of some of the same programs. (We show results for all of the v.2006-10-MR2 benchmarks and for those of the v.9.12-Bach benchmarks that could be analyzed by the DOOP framework in under 3 hours.) We also use two benchmarks (NTI, jFlex) from the Julia set by Nikolić and Spoto [19]. (The rest of the benchmarks in that set are Android applications, which the DOOP framework currently does not analyze for purely engineering reasons.)

We use the LogicBlox Datalog engine, v.3.10.14, on a Xeon E5-2667 v.2 3.3GHz machine with only one thread running at a time and 256GB of RAM.

Scalability caveats. The static reflection handling hinders scalability for *2objH*. When benchmarks did not terminate in 3hrs, we attempted to use DOOP’s (less precise) context-insensitive analysis, with the same time limit. The *jython* and *h2* benchmarks managed to complete in this setting. Conversely, the *5def* analysis did not complete in 3hrs for the *xalan* benchmark of the DaCapo Bach suite. We use a 4-call-site-sensitive (*4def*) defensive analysis for this benchmark,

Benchmark	Reachable application virtual calls	App. calls devirtualized by unsound 2objH (<i>*insens.</i>)	App. calls devirtualized, 5def ($\dagger 4def$) some context	% of 2objH (<i>*ins.</i>)	App. calls devirtualized, 5def ($\dagger 4def$) all contexts	% of 2objH (<i>*ins.</i>)	App. calls devirtualized, intra-procedural	% of 2objH (<i>*ins.</i>)
DaCapo 2006-10-MR2	antlr	17904	16999	8191	48.2%	6038	1623	9.5%
	bloat	14278	13425	4876	36.3%	4002	1459	10.9%
	chart	4073	3823	1034	27.0%	831	434	11.4%
	eclipse	6339	5711	2616	45.8%	2267	1186	20.8%
	fop	2307	2132	1120	52.5%	992	263	12.3%
	hsqldb	1166	994	588	59.2%	547	185	18.6%
	<i>jython*</i>	<i>14505</i>	<i>11444</i>	3690	32.2%	3191	1552	13.6%
	luindex	2249	2074	951	45.9%	882	358	17.3%
	lusearch	2756	2400	1091	45.5%	957	438	18.3%
	pmd	4801	4417	1930	43.7%	1704	806	18.2%
xalan	9135	7772	1781	22.9%	1262	543	7.0%	
jFlex	2734	2712	1195	44.1%	938	394	14.5%	
NTI	1067	954	487	51.0%	387	161	16.9%	
DaCapo 9.12-Bach	avrora	10910	10387	4892	47.1%	4270	1695	16.3%
	batik	17757	14387	5323	37.0%	3397	1694	11.8%
	eclipse	7923	6624	3024	45.7%	2605	1371	20.7%
	<i>h2*</i>	<i>23212</i>	<i>20107</i>	8820	43.9%	7814	2948	14.7%
	luindex	4958	4332	2059	47.5%	1805	630	14.5%
	lusearch	3687	3203	1654	51.6%	1388	594	18.5%
	pmd	6421	5760	2344	40.7%	2018	1002	17.4%
	sunflow	3303	3178	1170	36.8%	833	365	11.5%
	<i>xalan†</i>	<i>25198</i>	<i>21222</i>	5497	25.9%	4366	1997	9.4%
	<i>median</i>				44.8%			38.7%

Figure 5: Virtual calls resolved to a single target method by each analysis. Min/max percentages shown in bold.

instead of 5def. Our figures show numbers in *italics* for such special cases of analyses other than 5def/2objH (only 3 instances out of 44 total analyses).

Coverage. A defensive analysis is highly conservative by nature: it eagerly falls back to computing nothing (i.e., an empty points-to set) when it cannot guarantee to be over-approximate. Therefore, the primary question is whether the analysis can produce results for a large part of the program.

We apply the defensive analysis to all application methods deemed reachable by the unsound (2objH or insensitive) analysis. (This is just a benchmarking setup—the defensive analysis can be applied to any subset of the program code.) We then compute the *coverage* of the defensive analysis: the number of points-to sets that are non-empty, i.e., that the analysis successfully upper-bounds.

Figure 4 shows that the 5def analysis yields non-empty points-to sets for a significant portion of each program—the median benchmark has 45.6% of variables with points-to information for *some* context, while 35.5% have points-to information for *all* contexts. Both numbers are meaningful and the first probably more so. Recall that the meaning of inferences under *some* context is quite different for a defensive analysis: many of its useful inferences will be under *some* context even when the inference holds under *all known* contexts (since there may be other calling contexts in opaque, and possibly not yet existing, code). Thus, the defensive analysis achieves a large proportion of the benefits of an unsound analysis, while guaranteeing these results against

opaque code. Furthermore, the analysis is significantly more useful than a baseline intra-procedural analysis that soundly covers the easy cases of points-to reasoning.

Running time. The last two columns of Figure 4 show the running times of the analyses. As can be seen, 5def is competitive, and outperforms 2objH for 16-of-22 benchmarks, one is tied, and 2objH is faster for 5 benchmarks (also taking into account the 3 benchmarks for which either 2objH or 5def timed out). This confirms that a defensive analysis achieves scalability even for deep context by representing unbounded points-to sets as empty.

Points-to set sizes. Figure 4 shows average points-to set sizes for the analyses studied. The sets (excluding null values) are computed over variables covered by both analyses (for non-empty defensive analysis sets). The first comparison (first two numeric columns) is over variables that the defensive analysis covers for *some* context, while the second (next two columns) over variables that the defensive analysis covers for *all* contexts. Again, the use of context in a defensive analysis is different, so both numbers are biased, but in opposite ways. The *some context* comparison may exclude valid contexts for which 5def computes empty sets, making it seem more precise. Conversely, the *all context* numbers exclude variables whose points-to set depends on method parameters, thus downplaying the precision difference of 5def’s 5-call-site sensitivity. Still, the overall picture is clear: 5def is highly precise, much more so than 2objH.

Client analysis: devirtualization. Figure 5 shows the impact of the 5def analysis for a standard devirtualization client (resolving virtual calls to a single target method). This is the kind of client that can benefit from a sound static analysis. As can be seen, 5def manages to recover a large part of the benefit of an unsound analysis (median 44.8% for optimization under a context guard, 38.7% for unconditional, all contexts, optimization), performing much better than the baseline intra-procedural sound must-analysis (at 14.6%).

6. Conclusions

Static analysis has long suffered from unsoundness for perfectly realistic language features, such as reflection, native code, or dynamic loading. We presented a new analysis architecture that achieves soundness by being *defensive*. We expect this approach to open significant avenues for further work. The analysis architecture can serve as the basis of other sound analysis designs. The defensive analysis itself can be combined with several other analyses (may-escape, must-alias) that have so far been hindered by the lack of a sound substrate. The analysis can be enhanced with a wealth of extra information to extend its coverage.

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